

CARDEA

Career Acknowledgement for Research
(Managers) Delivering for the European Area
Grant Agreement No. 101058572

Training Catalogue - Initial suite – D. 7.1

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Authors	Barbara Chiuconi Erica Feliziani Francesca Spigarelli
Work Package/Task leader	University of Macerata

CARDEA MATRIX

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1 - CARDEA project in a nutshell

CARDEA: Career Acknowledgement for Research Managers Delivering for the European Area is a Horizon Europe funded project. Its overall goal is to contribute to the recognition, promotion and professionalisation of Research Managers roles, by outlining skills requirements, career pathways and appropriate developmental supports and recognition for those who choose this career.

More specifically, CARDEA will:

- Increase awareness amongst research management staff about existing training, networking and mobility opportunities at EU, national, and regional levels;
- Grow the capacity and compatibility of cooperation and funding systems throughout the European Research Area for research management, and support to scientists;
- Improve knowledge for policy-making about the training and networking patterns of research support staff and research management;
- Improve awareness of the EU policy drivers and the EU research peculiarity in the Higher Education Institutions and Research organisations;
- Establish central hubs to provide the EU research system with the most appropriate “fit for purpose” skills in EU research management, with active involvement of entities located in widening countries;
- Provide recommendations aiming at facilitating a clear career path for research managers at national and EU levels, enhancing their role towards the achievement of the new European Research Area objectives.

The project will contribute to Action 17 of the ERA policy agenda¹ “Enhance the strategic capacity of Europe’s public research performing and funding organisations”, which aims to improve the European R&I system across the entire ERA, by strengthening the capacity for research management in Europe’s public research performing and funding organisations. Therefore, CARDEA is a key component of the so called “Research management initiative”, launched by the EU Commission to enhance:

- **Upskilling:** improve training and skills of research management staff
- **Recognition:** contribute to professionalization
- **Networking:** support best-practice exchange
- **Capacity building:** support less R&I intense regions and organisations

Among the 9 work packages composing the CARDEA work plan, WP 7 “Training and development” aims to develop a comprehensive training programme designed by and for Research Managers, based on a deep analysis of RMs needs performed within the project.

This deliverable D7.1 “Training Catalogue – Initial suite” reports on the training needs for research managers, outlines the main training initiatives available for RM and illustrates the concept idea of the CARDEA training modules. These will be then developed in the next months, and will be duly reported in D7.2 “Training Catalogue – Midterm update”, due in M30. Moreover, in order to avoid overlapping with the project RM ROADMAP² (supporting Action 17 of the ERA Policy agenda as Cardea), it was agreed that RM ROADMAP will be responsible for the mapping of the existing training initiatives for RMs, whereas CARDEA will focus on the analysis of training needs.

¹ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/european-research-area_en

² <https://www.rmroadmap.eu/>

This analysis is expected to be very useful to describe the main features, needs, gaps related to the training ecosystem for RMs in Europe. Therefore, it will be the starting point for designing the CARDEA training modules. Moreover, it will be useful to others that have the same need to develop a training path for research managers and that from this analysis could get precious information.

As for the methodology used, CARDEA investigate RMs' needs via a two-fold analysis:

1. Analysis of the results emerged by EU and international surveys conducted in recent years and targeting RMs (see section 3.1 of this deliverable). Goal of this analysis is to gain a full understanding of training needs from the RMs' point of view.
2. Analysis of the needs and expectations of other key actors of the Research and Innovation systems: RM's employers, policy makers in the field of research and innovation, opinion leaders (see section 3.3 of this deliverable). The goal of this analysis is to understand training needs from the perspective of those who are interested in the enhancement of the support provided by RMs.

This second component of the methodology, less usual than the first one, was not explicitly foreseen in the Annex I of CARDEA, but it is necessary to avoid results that are self-referential (i.e. coming only from RMs). This investigation has just started but, thanks to the synergy with the network of the RM National Ambassadors within RM ROADMAP (just launched in May 2023), CARDEA plan to expand it across all EU countries. Nevertheless, CARDEA can already bring to the EU ongoing discussion some preliminary results that are illustrated in this deliverable and that the project team plans to complete within 2023.

2 - The EU context

The **ERA (European Research Area)** was launched in 2000 with the aim to build a common scientific and technological area for the EU where the creation of a single market for research and innovation is fostering free movement of researchers, scientific knowledge and innovation, and encouraging a more competitive European industry. Over 20 years, the ERA has seen major achievements such as the diffusion of research infrastructures, as well as the implementation of open science principles, international cooperation, gender balance in research and innovation, joint programming, research careers and the mobility of researchers. On 30 September 2020, the Commission adopted a Communication on '**A New ERA for Research and Innovation**', in which it proposes a revitalization of ERA, sets out a new vision and calls for mobilising Member States around key principles and values for identifying shared priority areas for action.

The Council Conclusions on the New ERA, adopted on 1 December 2020, called on the Member States and the Commission to develop in 2021 an **ERA policy agenda** and a multi-level governance model to deliver on the new ambition for the ERA. The ERA Policy Agenda, launched in November 2021, set out voluntary ERA actions for the period 2022-2024 to contribute to the priority areas defined in the Council Recommendation on a Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe. 20 actions organized in 4 priority areas (1 - deepening a truly functioning internal market for knowledge; 2 - taking up together the challenges posed by the twin green and digital transition, and increasing society's participation in the ERA; 3 - amplifying access to research and innovation excellence across the union; 4 - advancing concerted research and innovation investments and reforms) were proposed.

Among the 20 actions of the ERA Policy Agenda, for the **ERA action 17** "Enhance the strategic capacity of Europe's public research performing organisations", a **Science Management Initiative** was proposed to improve training and skills development of science management staff. This action intended to pilot a **European network for research and innovation managers** through Horizon Europe, explore European training and certification programmes, and provide policy support for Member States through mutual learning platforms on science management. The ERA 17 policy action works across four priority axes: 1) **Upskilling**, to improve training and skills of research management staff, 2) **Networking**, to support best-practice exchange, 3) **Recognition**, to contribute to RM professionalization, and 4) **Capacity building**, to support less R&I intense regions and organizations. Under the umbrella of Action 17, within the Horizon Europe work programme 2021-2022, the call HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-20 "Towards a Europe-wide training and networking scheme for Research Managers" funded the CARDEA and RM ROAD MAP projects aimed to achieve the 4 priority axes of ERA action 17.

The need of upskilling for research management staff is in line with the empowerment of training and lifelong learning enshrined in the **European Skills Agenda**, launched in July 2020. The agenda sets ambitious, quantitative objectives for upskilling (improving existing skills) and reskilling (training in new skills) to be achieved within the period 2020-2025, through 12 actions. The implementation of these actions is further promoted via the launch of the initiative of **2023 European Year of Skills**, whose aim is to make sure that European workforce skills are relevant for labour market needs. Member States have endorsed the EU 2030 social targets that at least 60% of adults should participate in training every year, already presenting their national contribution to meeting this target.

Among its 12 flagship actions of the European Skills Agenda, new initiative on a European **approach to micro-credentials** aims to support the quality, transparency and take-up of micro-credentials across the EU, in order to encourage people to upskill and reskill in a fast and effective way, in line with needs of the labor market and a fast-changing society. The micro-credentials answer to the need to reskill and upskill through more flexible alternatives than a full degree in order to overcome the gap between the learning outcomes of initial formal qualifications and emerging skills needs in the labor market.

3 - Training ecosystem for Research Managers

3.1 The scenario depicted by surveys targeting Research Managers

As starting point of CARDEA deliverable 7.1, a desk research was conducted to analyse the results of the main available surveys targeting RMs and investigating the ecosystem where RMs operate. Indeed, these surveys depict some aspects related to the training ecosystem for RMs. In particular, the analysis focuses on 5 recent surveys, namely CARDEA, first (2016) and second (2019) RAAAP, HETFA and EARMA surveys, and mentions some others.

These surveys were developed in different contexts and for different purposes, but all of them give an insight into the subject of training for RMs. The common characteristic of them is the fact that the participants of the surveys are RMs. Per each survey, an introductory paragraph to the context of the survey is provided, followed by an “identikit” of the respondents to the questionnaires (country, age, gender, education, and other relevant info) and then by a summary of the main findings concerning the training.

Just as clarification, the 5 surveys refer in some cases to soft skills, in some others refer to transversal skills. For the purpose of this deliverable, these words are used as synonymous.

3.1.1 CARDEA survey

Context of the survey

As a starting point of CARDEA project, it was first necessary to develop a detailed understanding of the contexts, challenges and opportunities that RMs face within and beyond the EU. Indeed, the CARDEA proposal was built according to a two-stage model. The goal of Stage 1 was to establish a solid data driven baseline of evidence to inform project activities, as there was little systematic data available about the needs and challenges of RMs. While Stage 2’ aim was to inform the development of solutions to meet the challenges.

The CARDEA survey belongs to stage 1’s actions. It consisted of a questionnaire of 97 items organized in 11 sections to ask RMs about their demographics, employment, skills and education, motivation and satisfaction and professional networks and mobility. The survey was launched in August 2022 and was open till the end of December 2022. Each of the CARDEA partners reserved the utmost commitment to widespread the survey through national and international associations of RMs, specific networks and own contacts and channels.

A specific CARDEA report³ summarizes the main results of the survey. In addition, all the questions of the CARDEA survey together with the raw data are available in Zenodo⁴ (Chrualaich and O'Regan, 2023). This section 3.1.1 collects and comments the main results concerning “training ecosystem for RMs”.

Survey respondents

The CARDEA survey targeted the RM’s community. In total, 855 responses were received. The 45,5% of respondents (389 responses) completed the entire survey in all 11 sections. 456 respondents completed at least nine of the sections (more than 50% of the total respondents).

Table 1 furnishes a summary of the main characteristics of the respondents that provided the information of CARDEA survey.

Table 1. Main characteristics of respondents of the CARDEA survey

Characteristics	Info
Gender	Female: 73.2%
Age	Average age: 43 years

³ https://www.ucc.ie/en/media/research/cardea/Cardea_Report_Summary_FINAL.pdf

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/record/7882908#.ZE-Edc7MKHs>

	Age groups: - 29 and under: 4.5% - 30-39: 28.5% - 40-49: 47.1% - 50-59: 17.6% - 60 and over: 2.3%
Countries	EU Nationals: 86.5% - Ireland: 17.7% - Spain: 16.3% - Portugal: 12.2% - Italy: 11.2% - Germany: 8% - Poland: 5.5% - Croatia: 4.3% - France: 3.1% - Belgium: 3% Other EU: 5.5% UK and Northern Ireland: 3% Rest of world: 4.9%
Education	PhD: 53.9% PhD and master: 90.8% Specific RM qualification: 19% Knows 2 languages: 79.1%
Years of experiences as RM	Over 10 years: 33% At least 6 years: 21% 4-6 years: 12% Less than 4 years: 34%
Other info	Work and live in country of birth: 87.6% Member of a professional RM Association: 42.5% Type of contract Permanent: 66% Fixed Term: 34%

Less than ten percent ($n = 49$) are dedicated to managing an individual project. Over a third of respondents ($n = 186$, 35.0%) provide specialised professional services to a range of projects, with a further $n = 67$ (12.6%) leading a team that provides specialised professional services to a range of research projects.

Main results concerning trainings

RM professional qualification

Participants to CARDEA questionnaire were asked about their research management and administration professional qualifications. 81.0% ($n = 460$) of respondents do not have any specific research management qualifications or certifications. The remaining 19.0% ($n = 108$) report a range of credentials, with the most popular shown in table 2. It is worth to point out that there is no significant relationship between professional qualifications and the highest level of educational achievement.

Table 2. Most popular RM certifications as emerged from CARDEA survey

Certification	n
Masters in Research Administration	26
Certificate in Research Management (CRM)	22
Bachelors in Research Management	8
Certificate in Leadership of Research Management	8

In addition to RM-specific certifications, participants were given a free text area to indicate other qualifications that support or assist them in research management activities. Many people indicated that their expertise in research management derived from experience of actively doing the job. In addition, several respondents referenced project management training from short courses to full master in project management. Prince2^{®5} was the most frequent framework mentioned. Finally, a small number of respondents indicated that training in English language and career development was a feature of their educational profile.

RM's skills

Within CARDEA survey the participants were asked to rate the importance of specific skills for an effective research management activity and whether they had been offered training in these skills. Respondents chose among a list of 90 skills, that were grouped into 9 families, based on a comprehensive review of the literature on research management and RM roles (see table 3).

Per each of the 90 skills, the participants were asked to value the importance of the skill for research management within a scale ranging from 1 "not at all important" to 5 "vital" and to indicate whether training concerning this specific skill has been available or not.

Table 3 reports the averages of the importance estimated by the respondents for the 9 skill families and the relative percentage of cases in which training has been available. It is interesting to note that albeit transversal skills are the ones perceived as most important for daily work for research management, in the meantime, they are perceived as the less trained. On the other side, a lot of training opportunities are available concerning "specialised knowledge for research performing organisational contexts", which is perceived as less important among the 9 families. These findings corroborate the ones reported by Tauginiene (2009) according to which transversal skills, such as problem solving and communications capabilities, are among the main skills and qualities that a RM should possess.

Table 3. The 9 skill families of CARDEA survey with the rating of importance and occurrence of training

Skill family	Mean of Importance for research management (from 1 "not at all important" to 5 "vital")	Available training (% of the cases)
Transversal skills	4,26	10
Relationship management	4,15	14
Project Management	4,12	28
Financing/Contracting/Compliance	3,97	22
Communication	3,87	17
Line management and supervision of others	3,81	14
Outreach and community	3,79	11
Technical skills	3,72	19
Specialised knowledge	3,66	50

Table 4 reports in cardinal order the 25 skills out of the total 90, that are perceived as most important AND in the meantime as the ones for which less training opportunities are available. Indeed, this ranking score is the result of the sum of two ranking scores, one categorizing the skill importance (from most important to less) and one categorizing the available training (from less available to most available). Again, it is worth to

⁵ <https://www.prince2.com/eur>

notice that the transversal skills including reliability, attention to detail, flexibility, proactivity, autonomy, problem-solving and efficiency, are placed on the top of the list. Moreover, among the other top-25 skills there are skills that, albeit they are not classified as transversal skills, can be assimilated to transversal skills as they are part of the relationship and communication sphere i.e. building trust within partnerships; collaborating for success; building and maintaining relationships with funders, partners or other stakeholders; networking; academic and community relationship support; teamwork; responsibility for engaging with key stakeholders; coordination of communication.

Table 4. Top-25 important skills according to CARDEA deliverable and their skill family of belonging

Cardinal position	Skill	Skill family
1	Reliability	Transversal skills
2	Attention to detail	Transversal skills
3	Flexibility	Transversal skills
4	Proactivity	Transversal skills
5	Autonomy	Transversal skills
6	Problem-solving	Transversal skills
7	Efficiency	Transversal skills
8	Building trust within partnerships	Relationship management
9	Collaborating for success	Relationship management
10	Critical thinking	Transversal skills
11	Openness	Transversal skills
12	Building and maintaining relationships with funders, partners or other stakeholders	Communication
13	Diversified knowledge set	Transversal skills
14	Decision making	Transversal skills
15	Motivation	Transversal skills
16	Strategic thinking	Transversal skills
17	Managing competing demands	Relationship management
18	Networking	Relationship management
19	Academic and community relationship support	Outreach and community
20	Values Appreciation	Transversal skills
21	Teamwork	Relationship management
22	Responsibility for engaging with key stakeholders	Outreach and community
23	Coordination of communication	Communication
24	Creativity	Transversal skills
25	Promoting or supporting mutual learning	Relationship management

Professional Development Plans and Continuing Professional Development

The questionnaire examined whether RMs have Professional Development Plans (PDPs), whether they engage in Continuing Professional Development (CPD) and asked about the kind of support that would be useful in a research management context. The core findings are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Key professional development data from CARDEA survey

	n	%
Do you have a PDP?*		
Yes, personal	164	40.2
Yes, institutional	77	16.0

Yes, from funding agency	3	0.6
Yes, a national initiative	2	0.4
No	220	45.8
Other	14	2.9
Have you undertaken any CPD in the last 12 months		
Yes, during working hours	168	35.8
Yes, on personal time	106	22.6
No	195	41.6
If you have completed CPD in the last year, how much time have you devoted to this		
None	23	8.8
<8 hours	41	15.6
9-40 hours	146	55.7
41-80 hours	20	7.6
>81 hours	30	11.5

**Note the values do not add up to 100% as several people have more than one type of PDP.*

Participants ($n = 480$) were asked if they had a PDP. Over half (51.2%) do have at least one type of PDP, with many respondents indicating they have more than one. The most popular PDP is a personal plan (40.2%), and the next most popular type of PDP is an institutional plan (16.0%). Less than 1% of respondents have a PDP linked to a funding agency or as part of a national initiative. The data suggest that RMs are twice as likely to have an individual PDP rather than one provided or supported by their employer or national or national level. While this reflects the proactivity and engagement of the cohort, it challenges a systematic approach to research management development. Additionally, 45.8% of respondents ($n = 220$) have no PDP at all. In the free text area, several participants indicated that this is topic that their institution is currently examining.

Participants were then asked about their engagement with CPD. 58.4% of respondents ($n = 274$) have engaged in CPD in the last year. This value is very close to the EU 2030 target that 60% of the adult population should be involved in lifelong learning and is substantially above the average engagement in lifelong learning by professionals⁶. This is an encouraging result that shows that RMs are invested in and proactive about learning. For those that have engaged in CPD, 35.8% ($n = 168$) have undertaken CPD during work hours, and 22.6% ($n = 106$) have engaged in learning on their personal time. 41.6% ($n = 195$) have not engaged in CPD in the last year.

Participants were also asked to identify other type of support that could be beneficial to completing research management responsibilities. Eighty responses were collected to this query, the highest response rate for a free text area in this survey. Several themes emerged. There was a strong indication that research management is under-resourced from a staffing and facilities perspective. Other respondents talked about networking – existing or potential. Two types of networking were identified. The first was developing a community of practice within the research management ecosystem; this type of approach would enable sharing of expertise and experience. The second was a structured way to facilitate collaboration between RMs and other relevant stakeholders (e.g. national contact points). The final theme that was identified was the continued need to recognition of research management as an established, defined career.

⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/-/DDN-20190517-1>

3.1.2 RAAAP surveys

Context of the surveys

The RAAAP (Research Administration As A Profession) taskforce was created to periodically survey RMs and collect and analyse data about the evolution of the profession at global level.

The first RAAAP survey was held in 2016, the second edition in 2019 and the third in 2022. The 2016 survey was funded by the United States National Council of University Research Administrators⁷ (NCURA) and was led by Simon Kerridge (University of Kent, UK) and Stephanie Scott (Columbia University, USA) as Co-PIs, and was supported by an international advisory group. In June 2018, the Council of the International Network of Research Management Societies⁸ (INORMS) formally endorsed the RAAAP survey as an INORMS initiative. The task force initially included many members of the 2016 RAAAP survey team. In the following years, it expanded to include representatives from each of the INORMS associations and also some other related associations.

In order to describe the evolution of some aspects of the profession over the years, a core section of the questionnaire asks the same questions in every survey. Other parts of the questionnaire change, focusing on specific subjects of particular relevance at the time. For example, the focus of the 2019 survey was “research impact”, while the focus of the third survey was “how I became a research manager and administrator”. The questionnaires and the raw data are available as open resources on “Figshare”⁹.

Since the results of the third survey are not fully available yet, this section analyzes the results of the 2016 and 2019 surveys only.

Survey respondents

In Kerridge and Scott (2018), it is pointed out that the RAAAP survey targeted only RMs that were association members, and it should be assumed that, generally, those who responded are members of (at least one) RM association.

For the 2016 survey, overall 2,691 responses were collected, from 64 countries; however only 19 countries had more than 10 responses, and 5 (Australia, Canada, Norway, UK, and the USA) had over 100 responses. While, in the 2019 survey, 4,325 research management and administration professionals responded from over 70 countries around the globe. It is important to note that, in both RAAAP editions, most of respondents were from the Anglo-Saxon countries and consequently the surveys’ results mainly reflect their views and could be less relevant for the European context.

The following two tables (table 6 and 7) furnish a summary of the main characteristics of the respondents respectively for the 2016 and 2019 surveys.

Table 6 – Main characteristics of respondents of the 2016 RAAAP survey

Characteristics	Info
Gender	Female: 77%
Age	Age groups: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- 24 and under: 0.4%- 25-34: 14.7%- 35-44: 32.2%- 45-54: 31%

⁷ <https://www.ncura.edu/>

⁸ <https://inorms.net/>

⁹ The results of the 2016 survey are available at the following link: https://figshare.com/collections/RAAAP_Research_Administration_around_the_Profession_data_sets_and_supporting_files/4022284 (consulted on April 2023); the results of the 2019 survey are available at the following link: https://figshare.com/articles/dataset/RAAAP-2_Datasets_17_linked_datasets_/18972935 (consulted on April 2023).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 55-64: 18.6% - 65 and over: 2.3% - Prefer not to provide: 0.7%
Countries	United States of America: 36.87% Europe (excl UK): 15.32% UK: 17.75% Oceania: 13.28% Canada: 9.52% Rest of the world: 7.25%
Education	PhD: 26.4 % Master degree: 40.5% Bachelor: 26.4% Specific RM certification: 20.2%
Role as RM	Leader: 21% Manager: 41% Operational: 35% Not sure: 3%
Years of experiences as RM	Less than 5 years: 25% 5-9 years: 29% 10-14 years: 20% 15-19 years: 13% More than 20 years: 13%
Other info	Employer University: 87% Research Institute: 6% Other: 7% Public: 77% Private non-profit: 22% For-profit: 1%

Table 7 – Main characteristics of respondents of the 2019 RAAAP survey

Characteristics	Info
Gender	Female: 75%
Age	Age groups: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 24 and under: 0.5% - 25-34: 13.6% - 35-44: 36.1% - 45-54: 30.2% - 55-64: 16.2% - 65 and over: 2.2% - Prefer not to provide: 1.2%
Countries	United States of America: 34% Europe (excl. UK): 23% UK: 12% Oceania: 12% Canada: 8% Rest of the world: 11%

Education	PhD: 28% Master degree: 24% Bachelor: 30% Specific RM certification: 24% Knows 2 or more languages: 46%
Role as RM	- Leader: 18% - Manager: 41% - Operational: 38% - Not sure: 3%
Years of experiences as RM	Less than 5 years: 28% 5-9 years: 27% 10-14 years: 22% 15-19 years: 11% More than 20 years: 12%
Other info	Employer University: 83% Research Institute: 8% Other: 9% Public: 78% Private non-profit: 20% For-profit: 2% Not sure: 1% Permanent: 81% Fixed term: 15% Other: 4%

Main results concerning training – 1st edition of the survey

Rating of skills

In the 2016 survey, respondents were asked to rate the importance of hard skills and soft skills needed to perform their job.

Specifically, in the survey the hard skills included:

1. Proposal development
 - Identifying, sorting and dissemination of funding opportunities
 - Preparing proposals for research funding
 - Budget development / costing and pricing of research proposals
2. Project support
 - Drafting, negotiating and accepting contracts and subawards
 - Dealing with project finances / monitoring sponsored project financial activity
 - Employing staff (e.g. researchers or research administrators) on externally funded research projects
 - Reporting to Funders
3. Translation
 - Supporting research impact: facilitating the use of academic research both within academia, and in the wider world

- Knowledge exchange and business development – helping academic staff to work with industry and other third parties to mutual benefit
- Technology Transfer: where new businesses are created, or businesses explicitly use intellectual property generated from research
- Supporting the delivery of revenue generating short courses, e.g. through budget development
- 4. Supporting post graduate research (PhD)/graduate/doctoral students
- 5. Policy and Governance
 - Contributing to research policy and strategy
 - Supporting internal or external research assessment (e.g. the REF in the UK, ERA in Australia)
 - Supporting research ethics and governance
- 6. Working with research information systems (e.g. MIS, ERA, CRIS)
- 7. Audit and Compliance
 - Supporting audit: including compliance, and internal and external audit support
 - Working with External Auditors / Making statutory returns (e.g. in the US - Uniform Guidance, Subpart F [A133])
- 8. Service Delivery
 - Managing a research support service / office / function

On the other side, the soft skills included:

1. Communication skills: it includes conveying information on policies clearly (verbally and written), report writing, preparing and conducting presentations, and tailoring communications to targeted audiences
2. Teamwork/Collaboration: it includes working closely with central and academic departments, in addition to promoting good teamwork of staff
3. Adaptability/Change Management: it includes identifying external changes early on, and developing strategies for managing change
4. Problem-solving: ability to identify problems and recommend solutions
5. Critical Observation: ability to analyse and summarize aggregated data to various audiences
6. Conflict Resolution: requires negotiation skills and finding peaceful solutions when two or more parties are in disagreement over something
7. Initiative Taking: being a “self-starter”, proactive rather than reactive, persistent in overcoming difficulties that arise in pursuit of a goal
8. Cultural and Diversity skills: being sensitive to diverse cultural perspectives and encouraging teamwork of diverse groups
9. Decision Making: the ability to make good decisions with missing or incomplete information
10. Taking Responsibility: accepting and demonstrating personal responsibility for compliance areas, and for staff
11. Project Management: assigning tasks and managing deadlines for an overall project goal (e.g. implementation of a new system, policy or procedure)
12. Mentoring and Coaching: providing advice and support for others either formally or informally

Research administrators holding leadership positions assigned high importance to their soft skills, rating them as very or extremely important in more than 90% of the answers. The same skills were rated as very or extremely important only by the 50% of respondents employed at operational level. Additionally, the respondents were asked when the skills that they have indicated as being most important were developed, i.e. if these skills were developed while in the position, through formal training and learning “on the job” or these skills were owned prior to the current position. Only 14% of the participants reported that these skills were developed while in the position.

When comparing the average of ratings of three “Proposal Development” hard skills versus the average of all of the soft skills, the survey showed that leaders and managers reported higher importance of soft skills as compared to the proposal development related hard skills. Whereas Operational roles reported a higher proportion of their hard skills as being more important than their soft skills. Kerridge and Scott (2017) concluded that those holding leadership positions in research administration give more importance to their soft skills than their professional hard skills.

Main results concerning training – 2nd edition of the survey

In the second survey (2019) the part related to the skills and their rating was omitted, but interesting questions concerning the usefulness of professional accreditations and the importance of alignment of education/experience in the subject area(s) that RMs support were added.

In the 2019 survey, it emerged the importance of having relevant skills for the position, and then further developing those skills and adding new skills after taking on the role. Skills are described to be 360-degree or wide-ranging and they even look like never enough for the role (Poli et al., 2023).

Usefulness of professional accreditation

Respondents were given a list of available professional accreditation related to research management and administration, and then were asked to evaluate those they achieved with respect to their professional relevance. These evaluations were not entirely positive. According to most of them, the professional accreditations did not have any relevance for gaining a promotion/a new job (58%), helping them in their current job (55%), giving them more confidence in their abilities (54%), or increasing their credibility with faculty/academics/researchers (53%). In addition, 42% of the respondents that do not have professional accreditation are skeptical on the usefulness of these accreditation for career progressions. Similar responses were obtained isolating only the European respondents.

Nevertheless, the first RAAAP survey revealed that those in leadership roles are more likely (32%) to hold professional certifications than those in managerial (22.5%) and operational (20.6%) roles. Therefore, there seems to be a link between professional certification and advancement within the RM profession. Kerridge and Scott (2018) have hypothesised that RM specific certifications have helped individuals progress into more senior RM positions.

Importance of alignment with the research areas supported

The respondents were asked if they consider important to have education/experience in the subject area(s) that they support. For example, if it is important to have a background close to natural and life science when supporting research implementation in that area. The minority of the respondents considered as no important the alignment (28%) while the majority gave a lot of importance (30%) or a relatively low importance (38%) to this aspect. This finding suggests that a technical training concerning the subjects of the research which is supporting is important and could justify the transition from the role of researcher to the one of RM in the same field of studies.

The recent paper by Poli et al. (2023) commented on the results of the 2019 RAAAP survey. The paper confirms that a career in RM is rarely an intentional choice, while it is described as “labyrinthine”. Overall, when respondents were asked how they came to work in research administration, less than a fifth made an intentional choice (19.8% of n=4,313), most fell into the position (59.5%), and some were moved into an RM role (9.9%), and the rest for other reasons.

Professional development classes

The respondents were asked if they have taken specific professional development classes (separate from academic courses and professional accreditation) and whether these helped their career or not.

The respondents selected the following specific classes listed in order of percentage of cases.

- Communication skills: 51%
- Project Management: 47%
- Teamwork/Collaboration: 40%
- Cultural and Diversity skills: 38%
- Adaptability/Change Management: 31%
- Conflict Resolution: 30%
- Stress Management: 26%
- Mentoring: 22%
- Problem-Solving: 20%
- Coaching: 20%
- Service Culture: 14%
- Taking Responsibility: 14%
- Other: 14%
- Initiative taking: 13%
- Language Skills: 10%
- Critical Observation: 8%

In the “free comment” space, many respondents gave positive evaluation of the attended professional development classes, which were considered useful for their career advancement.

3.1.3 HETFA survey

Context of the survey

A really insightful analysis was published in 2019 by the HETFA, the Hungarian Research Institute and Center for Economic and Social Analysis (Virágh et al., 2019). The investigation shed light on conditions, skills and competences needed by RMs, with the final goal to get enough knowledge to prepare and implement a proper European educational and research project.

Within this context, HETFA developed and circulated among European RMs an online questionnaire that consisted of 35 questions, covering the topics of demographics, educational and professional background, place of work, advantages and disadvantages of the job, recruitment, skills and competencies and RM-related trainings and associations.

The online questionnaire was made available for distribution between 21st of February and 20th of March 2019. The survey was circulated through the BESTPRAC¹⁰ mailing list consisting of 600 recipients being part of the network and/or having attended to any of its events and trainings. In addition, the survey was promoted via Facebook and LinkedIn for professionals.

The questions of the survey are available in the annex of the HETFA discussion paper (Virágh et al., 2019).¹¹

Survey respondents

The HETFA survey targeted the European RM's community. 136 respondents filled in the questionnaire, but only 89 completed it fully.

Table 8 furnishes a summary of the main characteristics of the respondents that provided the information of HETFA survey.

Table 8. Main characteristics of respondents of the HETFA survey

Characteristics	Info
Gender	Female: 72.3%
Age	31-50 years: 81.4%
Countries	Respondents came from 31 different European countries <ul style="list-style-type: none">- 35.6% Eastern countries (Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Hungary, Macedonia, Poland, Romania, Slovenia, Serbia, and Ukraine)- 33.9% Western countries (Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Iceland, Ireland, the Netherlands, UK and Switzerland)- 23.7% Southern countries (Cyprus, Greece, Italy, Malta, Portugal and Spain)- 6.8% Northern countries (Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Latvia and Norway)- No answers from Czech Republic, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Slovakia and Sweden
Education	PhD: 29.7 % PhD and master: 91.6% Specific RM certification: 6%
Role as RM	Manager: 49.1% Advisor: 18.2% Administrator: 14.5%

¹⁰ "BESTPRAC: The Voice of Research Administrators - Building a network of administrative excellence" is a European network of research managers that was initially funded by COST programme in 2014, cfr <https://bestprac.eu/home/>

¹¹ https://hetfa.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/04/Research-managers_final_0408.pdf

	At least 5 years of experience: 77% At least 10 years of experience: 38%
Other info	Country of origin is usually the same as country of work Member of a professional RM Association: 36% Public institute: 68.8% Private non-profit: 27.5% Private profit: 3.7% University: 60.5% Research institute: 24.8%

Main results concerning training

RM's skills and competences

Participants to HETFA questionnaire were asked which skills and behavioural competences were considered necessary to fulfil RM job. Specifically, they rated the following skills:

- analytical skills
- mediation, negotiation
- information management
- information search
- IT skills
- interpersonal skills, networking, influencing
- teamwork
- problem solving
- administrative skills
- initiation
- cultural and diversity skills
- English knowledge.

Similarly, the rating of behavioural competences were among:

- flexibility
- teambuilding, motivation building
- leadership, decision-making
- planning, strategic thinking
- assertiveness
- openness
- creativity
- efficiency
- reliability
- values appreciation
- ethics.

In addition to multitasking and English knowledge, problem solving, teamwork, interpersonal skills and information management were considered of outmost important among the required skills. As for the necessary competences, reliability, efficiency, flexibility and planning, strategic thinking, teambuilding and motivation building were considered as conditions for being a successful RM.

These results are in line with the ones obtained with CARDEA survey.

Moreover, the HETFA report underlined clearly that RM profession needs a wide variety of different skills and competencies. This is proven by the high rates of “rather important” and “very important” answers. Again, this finding are in line with the literature (Tauginiene, 2009).

Difficulties in recruiting and training RMs

The respondents were asked about their experiences in the recruitment of RMs. 61.6% of participants agreed or strongly agreed on the difficulties to recruit colleagues bearing the necessary knowledge and skills and only a minority of respondents (16.3%) experienced a huge number of applications from which they could select the best candidates. In the HETFA report, this phenomenon was justified by the lack of awareness and lack of clear professional profile as well as dedicated undergraduate educational programme, so that many people never identify RM job as an opportunity (Green & Langley, 2009).

In addition, 80.2% of respondents agree or strongly agree on the fact that the training of newcomers is a long process which needs a lot of investment. This shows the strong need for a formal training especially considering the wide variety of skills and knowledge needed for the job and the competitive, uncertain and volatile nature of the work environment. Nevertheless, according to HETFA respondents, many work environments and institutions lack training opportunities for beginners.

Training for RMs

Only 6% of respondents claimed to have a professional accreditation or certification related to RM. The HETFA report clarified that “specific certificate” relates to either project management, international or research and innovation project management or Prince2 project management. 52.9% knows about some kind of program or certificate, these usually being programs offered by national or European ARMA organizations or BESTPRAC.

36% of the respondents is a member of a RMs’ associations and usually use the services of the organization, including for training opportunities, knowledge exchange, study trips to other institutions, workshops, events for networking and other activities.

The respondents were asked what kind of training or education would be useful for becoming a RM (available options were a. short term training - less than 1 month long; b. long term training - less than 1 yearlong; c. vocational educational programme; d. module or educational programme at higher education; e. other postgraduate educational programme). The variety of answers reflected the problematic nature of setting a formal training for an ill-defined and fast changing job. Though some respondents pointed out that any training is better than no training, all in all they seemed to be rather skeptical about training content. Many thought the best way to learn is on-the-job. They felt that the content and length of training initiatives should depend on the educational and professional background of the candidate, as well as the institution they work for. Many felt that success in research management depends more on having the necessary soft skills, which are hard to get in a formal training. Some of the respondents considered formal training either not necessary, or not possible. They saw that the best is to have some kind of scientific background and the necessary soft skills, while hard skills should rather be picked up on-the-job. They thought what would really be useful is coaching and mentoring from a more experienced colleague.

For formal training, a **problem-oriented hands-on training** with case studies, examples, challenges and their solutions was considered as almost useful. In addition, according to respondents, flexibility was another

“must have” for training, that could be achieved by modules, which could be adjusted to the starting knowledge of the participants.

3.1.4 EARMA PDRC survey

Context of the survey

The results of this survey were presented in occasion of the EARMA conference 2022 held in May in Oslo. This survey launched in 2021 was carried out in the context of the EARMA Professional Development and Recognition Committee (PDRC) by an international team of RMs. The PDRC working group is active in monitoring the trends and novelties concerning the thematic of professional development for RMs treated under several aspects of professional accreditation, professional development policy, recognition of RM profession, education and training, system of review, quality assurance and evaluation, continuing professional development (CPD).

The purpose of the survey was to get an overview on training initiatives and needs of the RMs in Europe and beyond, in order to provide inputs for high quality training for RMs and to identify relevant topics, emerging skills and preferred training tools, according to RMs needs. The survey originated from the mapping of existing training initiatives of RMs associations worldwide, carried out by an Italian RMs working group in 2020 (Romano and Albanesi, 2021).

The EARMA PDRC survey consists of 32 questions and is available online¹².

Survey respondents

The survey targeted the RM's community. In total, 124 responses were received.

Table 9 furnishes a summary of respondents' demographic profile.

Table 9. Main characteristics of respondents of the HETFA survey

Characteristics	Info
Gender	Female: 79%
Age	Age groups: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 25-34: 14% - 35-44: 50% - 45-54: 31% - 55-64: 4% - 65 and over: 1%
Countries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 36.3% EU Southern countries - 28.2% EU Northern countries - 24.2% EU Western countries - 3.2% EU Eastern countries - 8.1% Rest of world UN Classification for Macro-Regions
Years of experiences as RMs	Newcomer: 4% 0-5 y: 26% 5-9 y: 25% 10-14 y: 32% 15-19 y: 8% +20 y: 5%
Role as RM	Leading: 6% Managing and coordinating: 56% Operational: 36% Other: 2%

¹² <https://www.surveymonkey.com/r/TX2VKQ9>

Other info	Type of contract Permanent: 54% Temporary: 44% Other: 2% Employer University: 73% Research Institute: 15% Other: 12% Public: 86% Private: 14%

Core results concerning training

The results indicated that RMs were active in participating in training courses. Indeed, 57% of respondents were aware of training courses for RMs in their countries. Most respondents participated in training courses at least once a year (35%), 27% every 3 months and 21% more often. 60% of the institutions of RMs promoted the participation of their personnel in training courses allowing for both training leave and financial support. Training providers were mainly national contact points, consultancy companies and national authorities. In Northern and Western Europe also RM associations were active in training.

Although 1-day trainings were by far the most common option throughout Europe and the world, other ideal training structure were proposed by respondents that indicated as preferred a flexible MOOC-type training with lectures available on-line and flexible assignments' submission, followed by a series of workshops over two years and a week-long intensive training.

The survey also indicated that the most influential factor in RMs' choice of training is its relevance to everyday work and the career advancement.

Most respondents were not aware of available accredited courses in their country. This could be due to scarcity of certified courses, but it underlined the necessity for a more effective circulation of information and the lack of a unique site of reference where to find news and data.

Finally, from the survey it emerged that 40% of respondents were trainer themselves and 25% of which had a certification to act as trainer or teacher.

3.1.5 Other surveys

Other surveys that investigate the training ecosystem for RMs and can potentially provide further insights are the ones listed below:

- [RI:train project surveys](#)¹³, aimed to identify priority training needs of managers of research infrastructures. The results of this survey were used to develop the RI:train staff/knowledge exchange programme;
- [RI:TRAIN Plus quantitative survey](#)¹⁴, targeting specifically top level managers who lead European or national initiatives but also sites (e.g. subnational or national nodes) to define an understanding about what makes Research Infrastructures and their Core Facilities institutions, a success and what is important to their members with diverse backgrounds, tasks, interests and training needs.
- [Professionals at the Interface of Science \(PloS\) survey](#)¹⁵, which is part of a wider research project that systematically analyses the context and impact of professionals in research and innovation ecosystems and their self-recognition within the PloS community. The overall aim is to contribute to the research studies concerning research management by providing an analysis of this missing part of the community, namely their identity, professional paths, and community representation (Santos et al., 2021)
- [The foRMAtion project output 1](#)¹⁶ which is a report including a survey targeting RMs, university teachers, interested researchers, students at HEIs to identify existing good and bad practices about the current educational and training programs, tools and methods for the empowerment of potential RMs, as well as to identify the conditions, skills and competences potential RMs need to acquire for the drafting and implementation of excellent EU projects.

¹³ <https://www.esfri.eu/project-landmarks-news/ritrain-surveys-training-needs-managers-ris>

¹⁴ <https://data.aussda.at/dataset.xhtml?persistentId=doi:10.11587/RBXAZ7>

¹⁵ <https://sites.google.com/view/survey-rmas-agencies/home>

¹⁶ <https://www.formation-rma.eu/results/>

3.1.6 Main findings from the surveys

The main features of the training ecosystem for RMs, as depicted by the analyzed surveys, could be summarized as follows:

- **RMs need vast range of skills.** When CARDEA and HETFA surveys' respondents were asked to rate the importance of a range of skills, they rated as "rather important" and "very important" the majority of the listed skills and the high frequency of these answers show that RM profession needs a wide variety of different skills and competencies. Similar results were reported in the RAAAP survey and this is confirmed also from the scientific literature. Indeed, all contributions agree on the fact that RMs need to have a vast range of skills and knowledge. According to Shambrook and Roberts (2011) a dedicated successful RM has to be multi-talented and mission-oriented. The most significant contributions dealing with the definition of RMs, their main professional roles and professional frameworks are included in the reference list.
- **Importance recognized to soft skills.** In the CARDEA survey, it emerged that transversal skills are the ones perceived as most important and crucial for daily research management work. However, albeit they are perceived as most important, **few training opportunities on soft skills are available.** In the first RAAAP survey (2016), RMs in leadership positions assigned high importance to their soft skills, rating them as very or extremely important in more than 90% of cases. In the same survey, the same skills were rated as very or extremely important only by 50% of respondents employed at operational level. The conclusion was that RMs in leadership positions place more importance on their soft skills than their professional hard skills. Similar results emerged in the HETFA survey, in which many of the respondents felt that success in research management depends more on having the necessary soft skills that are hard to get via formal training. Some of the respondents considered formal training either not necessary, or not possible. They saw that the best is to have some kind of scientific background and the necessary soft skills, while hard skills should rather be picked up on-the-job.
- **Lack of training opportunities for RMs.** In the CARDEA survey, 81% of respondents did not have any specific research management qualifications or certifications, 45.8% of respondents had no professional development plan at all, 41.6% have not engaged in CPD in the last year and, among those that have engaged in CPD, 22.6% have engaged in learning on their personal time. Similarly, the HETFA report underlines the lack of specific educational programs, which is reflected in the **difficulties to recruit RMs** bearing the necessary knowledge and skills. In addition, training of newcomers is recognized as a long process which needs a lot of investment. In the HETFA survey, only 6% of respondents claimed to have any kind of professional accreditation or certification related to RM.
- Training should be **relevant to daily work tasks** and should have a **problem-oriented and hands-on approach** with case studies, examples about possible challenges and their solutions. In the EARMA survey, ideal training structure were proposed by respondents that indicated a preference for a flexible MOOC-type training with lectures available on-line and flexible assignments' submission. Other preferred training options were a series of workshops over two years and a week-long intensive training. The EARMA survey also indicated that the relevance to everyday work tasks and career advancement is the most influential factor in RMs' choice of training. In the HETFA survey, respondents indicated that **coaching and mentoring from a more experienced colleague** is extremely useful. As for formal training, a problem-oriented hands-on training with case studies, examples, challenges and their solutions was considered as the most useful. Additionally, according to respondents, **flexibility** is another "must-have" for training. This can be achieved via modules that can be tailored to the background knowledge of the participants.

3.2 Training opportunities for Research Managers

This section gathers and outlines the main training opportunities available to RMs. This preliminary desk research will help CARDEA (a) map the research management training ecosystem; (b) understand its functioning; (c) devise and develop new and innovative training modules; and (d) add value to what is available by circulating information and increasing accessibility. In regard to project outputs, CARDEA and its sister project RM ROADMAP¹⁷ agreed on creating a unified online tool/repository. The repository will offer training, networking, mobility and funding opportunities available to RMs, increasing the searchability of and the accessibility to reliable and up-to-date information. It was agreed that RM ROADMAP will complete an extensive and systematic desk-based research on training, networking, mobility and funding opportunities available to RMs in the ERA and that the results of this research will be included in the CARDEA's online dashboard. In the upcoming months, the results of this collection will be available on the RM ROADMAP and CARDEA websites.

This section offers a brief and preliminary summary of the most relevant training opportunities available to RMs. The selection includes certified training opportunities linked to RM professional qualification and other relevant training options.

3.2.1 Certified training for Research Managers

Table 10 collects the most relevant certified training opportunities targeting RMs and offered by RM organizations across the world. In most of cases, the certification is linked to a professional qualification stage (i.e. basic, advanced, or senior level).

Table 10. Main certified training opportunities targeting RMs and offered by RM organizations across the world

Organization	Training Title	Brief Description	Website
EARMA European Association of Research Managers and Administrators	European Certificate in Research Management (CRM)	Training program targeted for RMs with at least 3-4 years' experience. It consists of 5 mandatory units as one-day physical workshops + 1 optional unit on line for a total of about 180 hours of study and submission of written assignments. Upon successful participation, a certificate and 20 ECTS are awarded. Beside CRM, other 2 professional development programmes are offered by EARMA: Early Stage Research Administrators Masterclass (designed for people who have recently moved into research support, 0–4 years' experience. 2 full days (in-person) or 5 half days (online) and Leaders in Research Management .	Link
ARMA Association of Research Managers and Administrators (UK)	Certificate in Research Management: Foundation	The training is an introduction to the research management profession open exclusively to ARMA members and sister associations. The format is a mixture of workshops and webinars, for a total qualification time of 240 h.	Link to factsheet
	Certificate in Research Management: Advanced	The training is for who have experience in research management, and specific responsibilities within their department or unit. The format is a mixture of workshops and webinars, for a total qualification time of 240 h.	Link to factsheet
PRAXIL AURIL UK's professional association for Knowledge Exchange practitioners	Registered Technology Transfer Professional (RTTP)	RTTP is the international professional standard for knowledge transfer and commercialisation practitioners working in universities, industry and government labs. To earn RTTP, it is necessary to demonstrate the core competencies needed to work effectively in the profession and an established track record including for RTTP training courses.	Link
	Candidate RTTP	Candidate RTTP is a designation that allows entrants to the profession to signal that they have committed to a pathway of training and development leading to the award of full RTTP status. It	

¹⁷ <https://www.rmroadmap.eu/>

Organization	Training Title	Brief Description	Website
		indicates to employers that they are serious about their career and aspire to meet the highest standards.	
SRA INTERNATIONAL Society of Research Administrators International	LevelUP Micro-credential Program	The program consists of training modules that are 2 to 5 hours in duration on topics most relevant to research administration professional. For each module completed, the students earn a micro-credential and a digital badge, thought 5 levels.	Link
	Certificate Programs	The SRAI Certificate Program offers comprehensive training in the field of research administration & management through 10 certificates. Each certificate includes a required half-day or full-day workshop and a specific amount of required and elective concurrent sessions.	Link
	Continuing Education Units (CEU)	Continuing Education Unit (CEU) is a recognized measure of participation in a continuing education program. A CEU is defined as 1 CEU per hour. Registrants will receive continuing education units and credit for all modules and plenaries they attend during the meeting.	Link
CARA – ACAAR The Canadian Association of Research Administrators	Research Management and Coordination Certificate	The program prepares graduates to move into positions of leadership within the field of research administration. The format is flexible, with fully-online program delivery. All students will have the opportunity to identify a Professional Mentor through the CARA-ACAAR or their own networks. The program is held in collaboration with the Canadian Mohawk College	Link
	Research Administration Certificate	The program is aimed at pre-management research administrators or those planning a career in research administration. Cover core components of research administration. Led by industry professionals, courses are offered in a flexible, part-time, online and interactive format that may include face-to-face live video conferencing. The program is held in collaboration with the Canadian Mohawk College	Link
ARMS Australasian Research Management Society (Singapore, Australia, New Zealand)	Foundation Level Accreditation Program (FLAP)	ARMS accredits the 3 levels with its own scale: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 25 points FLAP for new to research management/administration with less than 5 years experience; • 100 points ELAP for mid to senior Research Management Professionals who wish to enhance their leadership, management, and content skills; • 150 points ALAP for who are knowledgeable in their research management role and skilled in applying research management principles in their workplace. The programs comprise of a mix of taught material, group discussions and written assignments.	Link
	Established Level Accreditation Program (ELAP)		Link
	Advanced Level Accreditation Program (ALAP)		Link
RACC Research Administrators Certification Council	Certified Research Administrator (CRA®)	The RACC is a private, independent, nonprofit organization that develops and administers a voluntary program for the certification of individuals who meet the requirements established by RACC. RACC certifies that an individual, through experience and testing, has the fundamental knowledge necessary to be a professional research or sponsored programs administrator.	Link
	Certified Pre-Award Research Administrator (CPRA®)		Link
	Certified Financial Research Administrator (CFRA)		Link

Other RM professional associations and networks listed below - not exhaustive list - offer training programs for RMs, in some cases differentiated by the level of experience of the participants, albeit not linked to professional qualifications or certifications:

- [ARMA-NL](#), The Association for Research Managers and Administrators in the Netherlands
- [DARMA](#), Danish Association of Research Managers and Administrators
- [FORTRAMA](#), German Research and Transfer Management Network
- [Finn-ARMA Network](#), Finnish Association of Research Managers and Administrators
- [NARMA](#), Norwegian Network for Administration and Research Management

- [BE-ARMA](#), Belgian Association of Research Managers and Administrators
- [CZARMA](#), Czech Association of Research Managers and Administrators
- [ICEARMA](#), Icelandic Association of Research Managers and Administrators
- [Italian Research Managers](#) network
- [PIC](#), Plataforma de Interface à Ciência
- [RMAN-J](#), The Research Manager and Administrator Network Japan
- [BRAMA](#), Brazilian Association of Research Managers and Administrators
- [WARIMA](#), West African Research and Innovation Management Association
- [V4+WB](#) Network of Research Managers and Administrators from Visegrad Four (V4) and Western Balkan (WB) countries
- [INORMS](#), International Network of Research Management Societies

It must be noted that the Southern African Research & Innovation Management Association (SARIMA)¹⁸ offers training opportunities for RMs. Moreover, SARIMA has developed a professional recognition framework structured in 3 levels: Research Administration Professional (RAP) for new comers with 0-3 years of experience; Research Management Professional (RMP) for RMs at intermediate level with 3-5 years of experience; and Senior Research Management Professional (SRMP) for experts with more than 5 years of experience. Recognition in this framework is not strictly linked to the attendance of training. The professional recognition is entrusted by the International Professional Recognition Council (IPRC) which is an autonomous body composed by peers through the review of a portfolio of evidence, which includes prior learning, experience, functional and transferable expertise. The professional designation is valid for five years, after which it should be renewed or upgraded.

3.2.2 EU and international training projects and initiatives for Research Managers

The list below collects interesting training initiatives for RMs. Albeit some of these projects are over, the educational materials could be easily retrieved and used.

- [EUPM2](#) - A new academic path for EU Project managers: narrowing the gaps to enable better project design and management in Europe. Erasmus+ project: 1/12/2021-30/11/2024.
- [PATTERN](#) Empowering Open and Responsible Research and Innovation. HORIZON Europe project, call WIDERA 2022-ERA-01-44.
- [TrainRDM](#) - Open Science and Research Data Management Innovative and Distributed Training Programme. Erasmus+ project: 1/11/2020-30/4/2023.
- [RECAPHE](#) - Enhancing Staff Research and Innovation Capacity in Professional Higher Education. Erasmus+ project: 1/9/2019-31/12/2022.
- [OBERRED](#) - Open Badge Ecosystem for the Recognition of skills in Research Data management and sharing. Erasmus+ project: 1/9/2019-31/8/2022.
- [foRMAtion](#) - Innovative and smart module FOr potential Research Managers and Administrators in higher educaTION. Erasmus+ project: 1/9/2019-31/12/2022. As follow-up activities, the foRMAtion has launched two initiatives – [Alliance on the RMA Educational Module for RMA teachers and the Alliance on the Mentorship Programme for RMA mentors](#)
- [V4+WB](#) project - Network of Research Managers and Administrators from Visegrad Four (V4) and Western Balkan (WB) countries to contribute to their more successful participation in the EU R&I programmes
- [BESTPRAC](#) – COST project which is a targeted network that gathers administrative, financial and legal staff at universities and research-driven institutions who support transnational external competition based (in particular EU funded) research projects.
- [FORTHUM](#) European University Alliance that offers a series of workshops under the

¹⁸ <https://www.sarima.co.za/>

framework title “Professional Research Management in Multicultural Exchange”

- [Rltrain](#) - Tailored training for managers in research infrastructures project (2015-2020) developed a two-year European Masters in Management of Research Infrastructures (EMMRI) programme. H2020 EXCELLENT SCIENCE - Research Infrastructures
- [RITrainPlus](#) - Research infrastructure training plus aims at designing and delivering short-cycle Continuous Professional Development courses (CPDs) for current and potential leaders in RIs and to establish a permanent European School for Management of Research Infrastructures. H2020 EXCELLENT SCIENCE - Research Infrastructures

On the CARDEA website¹⁹, there are available training materials targeting RMs.

Other EU relevant projects are:

- [OpenInno Train](#) - Research Translation and Applied Knowledge Exchange in Practice through University-Industry-Cooperation. H2020-RISE MSCA project, 1/1/2019-30/6/2024.
- [RISE BPM](#) - Propelling Business Process Management by Research and Innovation Staff Exchange. H2020-RISE MSCA project, 1/5/2015-30/4/2019.
- [EM4FIT](#) - Entrepreneurial Management for Fostering Innovation and Talents. H2020-RISE MSCA project, 1/1/2020-31/12/2023.
- [BeingL S](#) - Meeting the challenges of delivering projects successfully in the 21st century. H2020-RISE MSCA project, 1/1/2017-30/9/2022.
- [HEIM](#) - Higher Education Internationalization and Mobility: Inclusion, Equalities and Innovations. H2020-RISE MSCA project, 1/1/2015-31/12/2017.

3.2.3 Main academic training for Research Managers

As reported in the HETFA Discussion Paper (2019), the existing programs available are for post-graduates or for professionals already working in the field, whereas apart from the Anglo-Saxon world, there is a huge lack of the educational programs of RMs. The following list, albeit not exhaustive, gives an idea of the vast possibilities of academic paths for RMs in the Anglo-Saxon world, while it underlines the need of training for RMs in the European context.

Some universities, mainly in US, offer training paths preparing for the job of research management. The list below, not exhaustive, offers an overview of some available academic trainings for RMs:

- [European Research and Transfer Management \(EURESTMA\) certificate](#), organized by an alliance of European academic providers
- [European Masters in Management of Research Infrastructures \(EMMRI\)](#) programme implemented at University of Milano Bicocca and developed within the H2020 project [Rltrain](#) - Tailored training for managers in research infrastructures project (2015-2020)
- [MS in Research Administration](#), Johns Hopkins University
- [Research administration](#), University of Maryland
- [Master of Science in Research Administration and Compliance](#), New York School of Professional Studies
- [Master of Science in Research Administration](#), “Emmanuel College” in Boston Harvard
- [Master of research administration](#), University of Central Florida
- [Researcher Management and Leadership Training](#), University of Colorado
- [Research Administration program](#), University of Montana
- [Research Administration](#), Rush University
- [Graduate Certificate in Research Administration](#), Central Michigan University
- [Professional Certificate \(PCert\) Research Management](#), Cambridge Centre for Innovation and

¹⁹ <https://www.ucc.ie/en/cardea/cardeahub/>

Development

3.3 Breaking the barriers: Research Managers' skills based on the perspective of the "others"

The 5 surveys analysed in the previous section 3.1 were all targeting RMs, so the respondents to the surveys' questions were all RMs. This circumstance may lead to generate results that are auto-referential, i.e. that do not take into account needs and expectations of all the other key actors of research and innovation ecosystems: researchers to be supported, research institutions and universities, policy makers and other stakeholders.

In order to enhance the quality of the services provided by RMs, investigating what the above-mentioned target groups expect from RMs (i.e. what skills RMs should have in order to fulfil their role) is key and strategic. The following sections carry out this investigation and gather information on the perception of research management and Research Managers by (a) policy makers in the field of research and innovation; (b) institutions and organisations hiring RMs; and (c) opinion leaders.

3.3.1 The perspective of policy makers

In order to have a complete overview of the perception of research management, CARDEA strategically analysed available policy documents at EU and national level that contain mentions, definitions or other descriptors of RMs and their profession. This analysis will provide useful insights on what policy makers expect RMs to do, what skills they think RMs need and, consequently, what training is necessary.

EU documents

The first analysed document is the Horizon Europe Work Programme 2021-2022, with particular emphasis on the WIDERA section²⁰. In the introduction, when speaking of the "brain circulation" phenomenon, there is specific mention to "research managers" that are at the service of the ERA. Additionally, in the description of the Twinning actions, in order to raise the research profile of an institution from a Widening country, special focus should be dedicated to the strengthening of research management, as this is considered of primary importance. In the ERA Talents call, in which secondments are open also to other research and innovation talents – such as administrative, managerial and technical staff supporting R&I activities into organizations, there is a description of "*other research and innovation talents' in R&I support capacity, such as knowledge brokers, data stewards, research managers, research infrastructure operators, knowledge and technology transfer officers, etc.*".

In the same document, under the description of call ERA-01-20 (the same call that funded CARDEA and RM ROADMAP projects), it is reported that "*research management can take many shapes: research policy advisers, research managers, financial support staff, data stewards, research infrastructure operators, knowledge transfer officers, business developers, knowledge brokers, innovation managers, etc. Entities and regions who are proven strong and excellent hubs in knowledge creation and innovation usually rely on a strong population of research managers.*". The same wording is present in ERA policy AGENDA of November 2021.

In the following Horizon Europe Work Programme 2022-2023 WIDERA part²¹, under the description of call 2024 ERA-01-03, the previous definition of research management was enriched with a revised list of roles: "*the research management takes various shapes across the ERA (and beyond), and therefore its definition/scope is multi-dimensional, including but not limited to the following roles: research policy advice, evidence-based policy making, foresight and strategy development; research coordination, research development, research project and funding management, financial support; evaluation and assessment support; research and complementary training programme management; data-based research support, such*

²⁰https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/wp-call/2021-2022/wp-11-widening-participation-and-strengthening-the-european-research-area_horizon-2021-2022_en.pdf

²¹https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/wp-call/2023-2024/wp-11-widening-participation-and-strengthening-the-european-research-area_horizon-2023-2024_en.pdf

as data stewards and data analysts, exploitation of research data, data protection; specialised research infrastructure operation; scientific integrity and ethics expertise, gender perspective support, legal support; science communication support; knowledge transfer and innovation support, knowledge brokering, incubator coordination and business development. In particular, the aim of this action is to further develop and implement a methodology to identify, train and 'professionalise' individuals who are essential support for the 'research enterprise'."

Moreover, the Work Programme 2023-2024 recognizes the strategic role of RMs in the research and innovation ecosystems, reporting that the "research performing and funding entities, local ecosystems, and regions that are strong in knowledge creation and circulation usually rely on a strong community of RMs, while lower R&I intense countries, regions, institutions often lack such communities, or do not have sufficient access to expertise."

Finally, albeit it is not a policy document, it is worth mentioning the ESCO (The European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations) website²², which describes and classifies professional occupations and skills relevant to the EU labour market and education and training, providing descriptions of over 3,000 occupations and 13,800 skills. In this website, there are definitions of these professional figures: research managers, research and development managers, grants management officers, public funding advisors, EU funds managers, policy officers, intellectual property consultants, data analysts, data scientist. On the other side, there are no definition of data steward, research infrastructure operators, technology transfer/knowledge valorisation officer (info retrieved on April 2023).

European national documents

Our next step was to use the CARDEA consortium as a pilot pool of resources for national policies. Specifically, each CARDEA partner was asked to collect its own national documents that were relevant to this purpose.

Table 11 summarizes the findings of this preliminary investigation.

Table 11. National documents that contain mentions, definitions or other items of descriptions that can depict the professional figure of RMs.

Country	Documents	Notes/definition of Research Managers
Ireland	Irish University Association Researcher Career Development Framework	The document reports that the research ecosystem includes researchers complemented by research support roles defined as "Research Officer" and "Research Assistant" (Page 17)
	Science Foundation Ireland's (SFI) Research Centres Programme	The programme includes provisions for funding of research management and research assistant personnel, named as project manager, IP manager, Education & Public Engagement Manager (Page 11)
	Irish National Research Policy	The document recognizes the importance of impact of talents for R&I ecosystem, but there is no explicit mention to RMs (Page 3)
Italy	National Research Plan 2021-2027	Concerning the new emerging professional figure of RM, the documents reports the following statements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> "Research Managers" will have to be the glue between the training systems at all levels, research, businesses and of the institutions, to promote and accompany the twin transitions, digital and green... (Page 29)

²² <https://esco.ec.europa.eu/en>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>The new generation of Research Managers will also have to accompany the transition to an open science and open innovation approach... (Page 30)</i> • <i>highly qualified Research Managers, who understand the languages of both worlds, that of science and that of business... (Page 30)</i> • <i>the training and recruitment of new professional figures to support research, for example, staff scientists, data managers, data analysts, facility managers and knowledge exchange managers... (Page 42)</i>
	National call for empowerment and capacity building of technology transfer offices 2022	The call foresees a new professional figure, named Innovation Promoter, which will have to play a linking role between the world of academic research and the world of industry. The Innovation Promoter has to act as an enhancer of patent titles towards companies potentially interested in developing and marketing innovations.
	National Recovery and Resilience Plan	The calls foresee the possibility to hire RMs for research projects, and the obligation to hire a infrastructures RM in the case of calls funding research infrastructures.
Poland	Public Employment Services Portal	In the governmental website, there are job posts for foreigners looking for working in Poland. Among other professions, the EU project coordinator is defined as <i>“the responsible for planning, managing and implementing the project, including timely achievement of planned results and settling the budget in accordance with the project assumptions. The coordinator organizes the work of project teams and is responsible for achieving the assumed goals of the project, coordinates and supervises the implementation of EU projects.”</i> .
Spain	Catalan Law of Science	In this document at Title III, Article 15, people in the service of science are defined as <i>“those workers who contributes to the research and innovation processes and to the maintenance and organisation of the spaces and instruments necessary for this task.”</i> .
Romania	International standard classification of occupations (ISCO-08)	Under code 1223 of the national classification of occupations the item “managers for research and development” is declined as “branch director for research and design”, “head of a research and design project”, “head of department for research and design”, “head of workshop for research and design”, “project director”, “head of project/program”.
	National Strategy for Research, Innovation and Smart Specialization 2022-2027	The document, that creates the premises and plans for the Romanian future of the research activities, mentions the professional figure of RMs/director. This strategy was transformed into a government law (HG nr. 933/2022)

Some of the CARDEA partners were not aware of specific national policy documents having these characteristics. Namely, the Greek and Croatian partners reported that such documents do not exist in their countries.

CARDEA survey

The CARDEA survey included a question asking if RM, as a profession, is a defined job title and role in the country of respondents, i.e. if RM professional figure is recognised by legislation or funded explicitly by research funders.

As reported in table 12, just over half of respondents ($n = 243$, 50.3%) indicated that research management as a profession is not a defined role in their countries e.g., is not recognised by the national legislation or funded explicitly by research funders. Only 25 participants (5.3%) indicated that 'yes' research management is a defined job title recognised by legislation or explicitly funded. The remaining responses were 'somewhat' 24% ($n = 116$), 'I don't know' 18.8% ($n = 91$) or 'other' (1.7%, $n = 8$), with one participant indicating research management as a profession was recognised "during early 2010s but in a last couple of years this diminished"; and another revealing that RMs are "in some cases funded by research funders (depends on the content of the job)".

Table 12. Responses to the question about whether research management is recognised as a profession at the national level. Data are separated by the membership of the EU, other European countries and responses from the rest of the world.

	Overall		EU		Europe not EU		Rest of world	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Yes	25	5.2	20	4.6	2	7.4	3	18.8
Somewhat	114	23.7	105	24.2	7	25.9	2	12.5
No	243	50.5	219	50.6	12	44.4	9	56.3
I don't know	91	18.9	83	19.2	5	18.5	2	12.5
Other	8	1.7	6	1.4	1	3.7	0	0.0

Conclusions

As the CARDEA survey highlighted, in the majority of cases, research management is not recognised as a profession by the national legislation nor funded explicitly by research funders.

However, the analysis of recent policy documents initiated by CARDEA reveals that RM are not so "invisible" as they used to be.

The European Union relies on RMs as key actors contributing to the excellence of the research and innovation process in EU (see Action 17 of ERA policy agenda). Moreover, in the WIDERA work programme, it is explicitly reported that entities who are strong in research performance rely on a strong community of RMs, while lower R&I intense countries, regions, institutions often lack such communities. Moreover, in ERA Talent call, secondments are open also to administrative, managerial and technical staff supporting R&I activities. The EU documents report a long list of various shapes of research management across the ERA ranging from research policy adviser to data analysts, specialized research infrastructure operator, scientific integrity and ethics expert... to cite some of them.

At national level, the preliminary analysis conducted by CARDEA revealed that RMs are seen by policy makers as figures that connect the dots of the worlds of science and of business. The RM are seen as the one that have to promote and support the twin transitions, digital and green and the ones who have to accompany the transition to an open science and open innovation approach (Italy). In the Polish, Romanian and Catalan documents RMs are seen as the organizers of the resources, often linked to the realisation of projects (both physical such infrastructures, and human resources).

Next steps

Albeit not specifically foreseen in the CARDEA workplan, this specific research on the policy makers' perspective will progress in the upcoming months. It will involve National Contact Points and the CARDEA sister project RM ROADMAP, in order to complete and/or expand the investigation on further national documents of all European countries. To this end, CARDEA plans to involve the community of ambassadors created recently within the RM ROADMAP project to collect these documents. RM ROADMAP ambassadors system conveys senior RMs across Europe, which were selected for the purpose of RM ROADMAP project by a dedicated committee, because of their experiences in the profession. More specifically, per each European country, up to two ambassadors were selected, assuring thus a good EU geographical coverage. The first kick off meeting of the ambassadors was on the 9th of May 2023 in Budapest, concomitant with the ERA Action 17 second workshop on RMs' upskilling.

In the framework of the joint collaboration between CARDEA and RM ROADMAP, in autumn 2023 the ambassadors network will collaborate with CARDEA to collect and analyse these documents.

3.3.2 The perspective of Research Managers' employers

The second step of this analysis is to investigate what skills the institutions and organisations hiring RMs expect them to have at recruitment stage.

The surveys analyzed in the previous section revealed how difficult the recruitment process of RMs could be. Specifically, in the HETFA survey, the respondents were asked about their experiences in the recruitment of RMs. 61.6% of participants agreed or strongly agreed on the difficulties to recruit colleagues bearing the necessary knowledge and skills and only a minority of respondents (16.3%) experienced a huge number of applications from which they could select the best candidates. In addition, in the same survey, 80.2% of respondents agree or strongly agree on the fact that the training of newcomers is a long process which needs a lot of investment.

This analysis, focusing on the RMs' recruitment, was planned getting inspiration to the CEDEFOP projects. CEDEFOP is the European Union's reference centre for vocational education and training, whose mission is to support development of European vocational education and training policies and to contribute to their implementation. According to their approach, within a context of dynamic and complex labour markets, gathering intelligence on current and future skill needs support better matching of training and jobs. Indeed, the anticipation and the matching approaches can help to develop tailored training for specific skills' in response to labour market needs. Among proposed CEDEFOP methodologies to forecast current and future skills needed by the job market, a leading strategy was the launch of "skills surveys" targeting employers. These skills surveys are considered particularly valuable for education and training providers (public or private) that could receive updated information on skills demand and therefore a precious support in the design of training programs.

Following the advices reported in the CEDEFOP "User guide to developing an employer survey on skill needs", CARDEA strategically will develop a survey targeting RM' employers. Among the RM's employers, were identified senior RMs that are involved in the recruitment of new RMs within a RPO. As done for the collection of policy documents, CARDEA will involve its community of practice and the community of ambassadors created within the RM ROADMAP project. Indeed, the RM ROADMAP Ambassadors system conveys senior RMs across Europe, which were selected for the purpose of RM ROADMAP project by a dedicated committee, because of their experiences in the profession. The questionnaire developed by CARDEA partners according to CEDEFOP methodology will be launched within the RM ROADMAP community of ambassadors by Autumn 2023. The survey will focus on the recruitment processes, the needed skill, the difficulties in recruitment and how to overcome them. The results of the surveys will be analyzed by CARDEA and will be collected in the next deliverable 7.2 which is due on M30 of CARDEA project, November 2024.

The results of a desk-based research study on recruitment advertisements for RMs

This section summarizes some of the preliminary results of a desk-based research study on recruitment advertisements for RMs carried out by Martha M. Phelan. Martha M. Phelan is a RM working at UCC in the Office of Vice President for Research and Innovation and concomitantly postgraduate student undertaking her thesis dissertation on the topic entitled 'What is it like to be a Research Manager: a phenomenological exploration of European research management and administration'. The purpose of her study was to gather information about job descriptions, roles and responsibilities as well as other pertinent information from different research sectors targeting candidates for positions as RMs or managers of research functions. The researcher monitored and sought through the use of key words (i.e. Research Manager, Research and/or Manager) recruitment agencies website and social media platform such as LinkedIn, to receive recruitment advertisements for jobs in these areas, over an eight-month period from September 2022 to April 2023. She analysed 11 job advertisements she has found and carried out quantitative analysis using MS Excel itemising

key words (and variations) and filtering the number of occurrences from the highest to the lowest. Among the required essential skills/qualifications, the key words (& their variations) found (ranging from the highest to the lowest, with items with the occurrence of less than 5 times not reported because not representative) included experience, management, research, project, team, leadership, communication, planning, strategic, and problem-solving.

These findings corroborate the ones obtained by the CARDEA survey and other surveys, according to which the essential skills for RMs are related to the transversal skills. Specifically, from the CARDEA survey, the top 25 skills vital for RM's daily work included, among others, autonomy, decision making, problem-solving, critical and strategic thinking, teamwork.

3.3.3 The perspective of opinion leaders

In order to better understand the role of RMs, based on the perspectives of the other actors of a research and innovation ecosystem, CARDEA expanded the scope of the investigation to include some key figures that were named “opinion leaders”.

Opinion leaders are experts of the ERA principles and in the meantime persons that know very well both the researcher profession (and, consequently, researchers’ needs), and the valuable contribution that research managers can give to research ecosystems.

Their perspective is important to CARDEA to deepen what the real expected skills for RMs are, with the ultimate goal of shaping training modules for RMs based on researchers’ needs. Indeed, these opinion leaders have a comprehensive overview of the whole scenario composed by the ERA, the researchers and the RMs. They can link the dots of the multiple needs of these three stakeholders.

Having this goal in mind, CARDEA decided to involve in their analysis the ERAC (European Research Area and Innovation Committee), since this is the EU's strategic policy advisory committee on topics related to research and innovation. And among the six ERAC sub-groups, which are in charge of advancing and monitoring specific ERA priorities, CARDEA decided to involve members of the Standing Working Group on Human Resources and Mobility (SWG HRM), specifically the experts that are participating in the review of the European Charter for Researchers and Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers (C&C).

In the upcoming months (June-October 2023), CARDEA will carry out brief interviews with these people. Our goal is to understand their feelings about the future of RM’s profession and how it should evolve in response to the needs of EU researchers and ERA priorities. The interviews will last about a half hour, with 2-3 initial standard questions for all interviewees followed an open discussion. The interviews will be on-line and recorded. The recordings and the core results of the interviews will be available in open data repositories.

4 - CARDEA training modules: concept idea

As mentioned in the introduction, the overall objective of CARDEA work package 7 “Training and development” is to develop a comprehensive training programme designed by and for RMs, based on the deep analysis of RMs needs.

Needs of RMs have been duly investigated by analysing the results of recent surveys, including the one conducted by CARDEA, targeting only RMs (see section 3.1 of this deliverable).

However, in order to further guarantee the quality and effectiveness of the CARDEA training, CARDEA strategically considered also needs and expectations of other key figures working with RMs (i.e. researchers, research institutions, universities and other stakeholders). This investigation, quite unusual in the EU to date, is in its preliminary phase (see section 3.3). Nevertheless, interesting insights that will be reported in the future update of this deliverable are expected.

Based on the two analytical approaches described above, this section provides the main features of the future CARDEA training modules. This analysis and the justifications supporting these choices could be useful to others that are planning a training path specifically tailored to RMs.

4.1 Target

The exclusive target group of CARDEA training modules are RMs.

Currently, there are many training courses that are delivered for researchers and open to RMs or vice versa. CARDEA does believe that RMs need a specific training enabling them to better support research and researchers, and that the recognition of RM profession is marked also by this “cultural” change. No one would even think to organize a training event for nurses which also targets doctors and vice versa. For sure, there would be some common topics, but the level of detail and the learning objectives are different!

Designing contents specifically for RMs means, for example, that topics such as those ones related to the EU research policies (Open science, gender-oriented research, etc) are addressed in a way that that specific topic is introduced and deepened, and then RMs learn how to provide a high quality support to researchers with regard to it (through e.g. the presentation of best practices and concrete cases).

Within the target group of RMs, CARDEA training modules will target both **senior** and **early-stage research managers**, including **newcomers**. The goal is to develop several training modules that are all together a comprehensive training to people new in the profession – a sort of **core learning** common to all categories of RMs - but concomitantly useful to more expert staff that could choose some topics according to their own needs.

A comprehensive training for newcomers is an added value as:

- It is a one-stop shop for employers that otherwise have to rely on different training providers and spend time and effort to train newcomers. In the HETFA survey, 80.2% of respondents agree or strongly agree on the fact that the training of newcomers is a long process which needs a lot of investment especially considering wide variety of special skills and knowledge needed for the job and the competitive, uncertain and volatile nature of the work environment.
- it is a sort of self-assessment tool that newcomers can use to understand their role and which skills are needed when applying for the job. It can set the expectations about the job.
- once it is completed, it is a proof of evidence to demonstrate the knowledge and an initial experience into the topics of research management and it is useful during selection processes both to employer and aspiring employee.

4.2 Format

The CARDEA training programme will consist of 16 **modules** to be delivered through **free on-line webinars**. The format of webinar embraces both the possibility to attend it in real time, but also the possibility to record the training and enjoy it on-demand.

The choice of this format is aligned to the need of **flexibility of content**. The context in which RMs operate is complex and variable and training modules should reflect this context. Among the several training modules, a RM could select specific topics according to their own needs. Indeed, according to the HETFA survey, the respondents envisaged a formal training in which the critical question is not length, but rather flexibility and practicality. For the flexibility they proposed the structure in modules, which could be tailored to the background knowledge of the participants.

This choice was also done to make the training more **inclusive**. Participation through on-line webinars allows all potential participants to enjoy the training, without sustaining costs related to travel and accommodation. In this sense, CARDEA will offer a “democratic training”, since it will offer a high-quality training for all, especially for RMs that are at the beginning of their career and could not have specific funds available dedicated for training (this is often the case of RMs from Widening countries or from small organisations, e.g. associations, NGOs). In addition, the improvement of the quality of the training means in the long run to improve the quality of research support, and this is a way to spread the excellence across Europe according to the principle that “none must be left behind”.

In addition, in the EARMA PDRC survey it was reported that, although 1-day trainings are by far the most common option throughout Europe and the world, other ideal training structure were proposed by respondents that indicated as preferred a flexible MOOC-type training with lectures available on-line and flexible assignments’ submission, followed by a series of workshops over two years and a week-long intensive training.

Modules will be designed with a problem-oriented approach, with a rich presentation of case studies, concrete examples, where possible challenges and their possible solutions are presented and discussed together. Moreover, in addition to the CARDEA training modules, there will be side by side the activities of the CARDEA Community of Practice, and other CARDEA initiatives to foster networking among participants. More specifically, the training modules will be linked to the subgroups of the CARDEA community of practices, that will act as a sort of **mentorship programme**, where participants to the training modules will find support and advice regarding the topic covered in the modules.

This choice is supported by evidence highlighted in the HETFA survey that reported that the mentorship programme can enable participants in getting into real life situations and receive tailor-made support from experienced mentors. In this survey, the respondents indicated coaching and mentoring from a more senior colleague as really useful.

4.3 Content

In order to better address the needs of the entire research and innovation ecosystem, the specific content of the CARDEA training modules will be decided according to the findings emerging by future investigations aimed at getting insights about the requested skills of RMs (see section 3.3) and will duly be illustrated in Deliverable D7.2 “Training Catalogue - Mid Term Update”, ready by M30.

However, the CARDEA consortium has already developed a concept idea of its contents and learning objectives, that are summarized as follows:

- The foreseen 16 CARDEA modules will compose a **comprehensive training covering the main topics** of RM profession and that will provide to (potential) newcomers a high-quality and complete training useful to start the profession. This training will be particular helpful also for RMs' employers, that will not have to spend money and also time to conceive a comprehensive training for the newcomers, as it currently happens.
- Learners will be free to choose whether to attend all the 16 modules or to attend one or more modules. Therefore, CARDEA training will be useful also to more expert staff that will **choose some specific topics according to their own needs**. To sum up, a RM could attend the whole package of training or select only the content of interest.
- CARDEA will pay a specific attention to design a training module concerning the **role and professional identity of RM**. This module will aim to describe the position of RM into the R&I ecosystem, especially to newcomers, for whom becoming a RM is rarely an intentional choice, and, in general, to raise awareness about the existence of the profession.
- According to the initial CARDEA proposal that was submitted to the call, CARDEA was supposed to develop training modules on topics concerning UNSDG, Outreach and Engagement, Smart Specialisation, EU policy and R&I ecosystem and funding instruments, twin priorities, Research Integrity. However, the choice of these topics will be evaluated and revised on the light of the results of investigations about expected skills of RMs (see section 3.3) and by the insights that could emerge from the sister project RM ROADMAP.
- The CARDEA survey highlighted the lack of training on **soft skills**, albeit perceived as most important. Although seem hard to train soft skills through formal training, proper training on these subjects could support RM in developing them and use them in the daily work. On the CARDEA website²³, UCC already made available some trainings on soft skills. CARDEA will rely on these materials and it will develop new specific modules on the subject. For example, a module on team working/ building i.e. on how to work with all the actors of R&I ecosystem.
- An innovative module on **“How to embed the Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R) in the overall research management”** will be part of the CARDEA training. Since all CARDEA partners have huge expertise on the HRS4R initiative, this module will teach how to make sure that the enhancement of the research management support is part of the overall effort of a research organization to improve its research environment. More specifically, it will learn on how to leverage on the HRS4R initiative to create synergies among the different departments dealing with research management and maximize its impact. In addition, the training module will teach how to make a research organization more friendly for RMs and attract the best talented research managers, by endorsing the CARDEA RM Charter and Concordat that will provide a set of principles and requirements for RMs (both public and private) employers.

4.4 Trainers

The CARDEA training modules will be developed by the CARDEA partners. According to the initial CARDEA proposal, 16 training modules should be developed, and being the partners 8, each partner should develop 2 modules.

The common ground of CARDEA partners is their experiences in the “Human Resources Strategy for Researchers, **HRS4R**”. It is not a case that the CARDEA consortium was initially built by a RM group with a proven track record in the delivery of initiatives to support research staff within partners' own university and organizations. It will be reflected into the CARDEA training modules' content that will be developed within

²³ <https://www.ucc.ie/en/cardea/cardeahub/>

the framework of “How to embed Excellence in research in the overall research management”. This content can legitimate CARDEA partners to act as EU trainers on the subject.

4.5 Certification

CARDEA training modules will be certified through micro-credentials which are, according to the EU definition, the record of the learning outcomes that a learner has acquired following a small volume of learning (a EU approach to micro-credentials, December 2021). The micro-credentials will be recorded in an open badge that will be issued by the University of Macerata, leader of CARDEA WP 7 “Training and development”.

The choice of micro-credentials and open badge are justified by its flexibility and practicality, especially for the participants to the training. Indeed, they can select the modules according to their needs and easily show the competences acquired through the open badge. The micro credentials recorded in the open badge will be a proof of the acquired competences.

Having said that, the attendance to CARDEA training modules will not prove the stage of career maturity (for example basic, advanced, leader level), being the career paths and backgrounds of RMs so diversified. The CARDEA position on this subject could be summarized by an answer collected in the CARDEA survey, that stated: *“I would like to see it (referring to the RM profession) regarded less as a profession which requires certificates and stamps and more as a craft which requires work experience and a range of skills which are not necessarily obtained in coursework. I do think of research management as a profession in many ways, but it can be so wide in scope that I feel it's difficult for it to be effectively learned through coursework and certification alone. I am effective because of my diverse background, not because I have a diploma in RM.”*

Albeit CARDEA training modules will not certificate career maturity level, CARDEA recognizes the importance of a professional accreditation/qualification and the need of training as formal education programmes (for example the CARDEA training modules, bachelor degrees, master degrees, other professional qualifications, see section 3.2) or other forms of training, such as mentoring programmes.

In order to develop its own identity, the RM profession needs a formal recognition, not necessary linked to the attended trainings. In the Southern African Research & Innovation Management Association (SARIMA), the professional recognition, structured in 3 levels, is entrusted by the International Professional Recognition Council (IPRC). IPRC is an autonomous body composed by peers that awards professional recognition through the review of a portfolio of evidence. Training, formal or not, belongs to the portfolio of evidence that are evaluated by peers, but it is not the unique criterion, indeed competencies, experience, contributions, and achievements are evaluated as well. Hence, in the SARIMA model, the attendance of a specific training does not automatically gives access to the basic, advanced or leader level of RM career. Each training experience is evaluated by the Technical Review Committee, composed by peers that know well the RM’s ecosystem, including for the training ecosystem.

A similar approach is held by the PRAXIL AURIL professional association, according to which the status of RTTP (Registered Technology Transfer Professional) is awarded by a peer review committee that evaluate the proven record of achievement of candidates. In this way, the RTTP framework recognises demonstrated competence and experience across the breadth of knowledge exchange, from IP commercialisation through to university business collaboration and start-up company creation. RTTP signals personal and professional credibility, and tells employers, colleagues and business partners worldwide that the accredited person is an experienced, skilled professional with a proven record of achievement.

Similar approaches exist for research careers in the ERA. In the Italian university system, for example, access to the next career level for university professors is awarded by a committee of peers that evaluate the

portfolio of main achievements. The evaluation by peer is necessary because of the complexity of the object of the evaluation (i.e. research achievements). This object makes an evaluation by external staff or standard metrics extremely difficult. In the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA, 2022)²⁴, peer review is recognized as the most robust method for assessing research quality and evaluate the diversity of research activities and practices.

²⁴ https://coara.eu/app/uploads/2022/09/2022_07_19_rra_agreement_final.pdf

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Competences frameworks organizing RM’s competences and related skills.

- ARMA Professional Development Framework for Research Managers and Administrators²⁵.
- RItain project developed framework for managers of research infrastructures²⁶.
- Italian professional framework for RMs developed within a working group of CODAU (Association of General Directors of Italian Universities)²⁷.
- CARDEA RM professional framework (to be delivered in D2.4 “Initial Cardea Toolkit report” expected by M30)

²⁵ <https://arma.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/PDF-Final.pdf>

²⁶ <http://ritrain.eu/competency-profile>

²⁷ <https://zenodo.org/record/5513738>